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Document type:	Statement
Title:	Food and Consumer Product Safety Authority (VWA) to investigate possible health effects of nano-silica particles in food
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Country	The Netherlands
Please refer to this document as follows	Statement of the Director of the Office for Risk Assessment of the VWA on possible health effects of nano-silica particles in food, November 2010

STATEMENT

Food and Consumer Product Safety Authority (VWA) to investigate possible health effects of nano-silica particles in food

Studies have shown that the dimensions of 33% of the silica particles added to food (E551) are such that they can be considered nano-silica particles. Little is known about the health effects of nano-silica particle intake. The Office for Risk Assessment and Research of the Food and Consumer Product Safety Authority has commissioned further research in this area.

Silica in food

Silica (E551), also known as silicon dioxide, is finely powdered purified sand and is used as an anti-caking agent in dried food, such as ready-to-eat meals, instant soups and coffee creamer.

The Office for Risk Assessment and Research has asked research institutes RIVM, RIKILT and MiPlaza whether the silica added to food could be traced in the end product in the form of nano-particles.

Research revealed that the dimensions of 33% of the silica particles added to food were such that they could be considered nano-silica particles. Humans may thus ingest a maximum of 124 mg nano-silica particles per day.

In 2009, ESFA reported that a daily silica intake of 1500 mg did not pose a health risk. It did not, however, make a separate risk analysis for nano-silica particles.

Further research

It is not clear yet whether nano-silica particles dissolve in the mouth or stomach. If so, they will not pose a risk according to the ESFA recommendations. However, if these particles do not dissolve but remain intact and are taken up by the body, the effects on human health are not clear. This will have to be studied further. VWA will publish the outcome of this study in 2011.

Reference to the publication:

Susan Dekkers, Petra Krystek, Ruud J. B. Peters, Daniëlle P. K. Lankveld, Bas G. H. Bokkers, Paula H. van Hoeven-Arentzen, Hans Bouwmeester, Agnes G. Oomen. Presence and risks of nanosilica in food products. *Nanotoxicology*, 2010. doi: 10.3109/17435390.2010.519836.